

Implementation of Freedom to Play Curriculum 2013 Early childhood education programs

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Abstract:- This study aims to explore the application of the concept of Independence of Playing in the 2013 Curriculum in an Early Childhood Education (PAUD), using a descriptive-qualitative method. The data collection was carried out using interview instruments, questionnaires, and direct observation to institutions to see the teaching and learning process and conduct documentation. The data analysis used was triangulation, by performing several stages, namely reducing the data obtained, presenting the data, and drawing conclusions or verification. The results show that the implementation of the Independence of Playing in the 2013 Curriculum, beginning with the preparation of the Semester Program, Weekly Learning Implementation Plans (lesson plan), Daily Learning Implementation Plans, and Assessment Planning which are carried out at the beginning of the school year when preparing the 2013 PAUD Education Unit Level Curriculum at PAUD *Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa*. The teaching and learning process with Independence of Playing is carried out when stepping before playing, playing activities, and communicating stages. The stakeholder of *PAUD Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa*, the principal, and the teachers work together in designing learning tools. After the unit-level curriculum is completed, educators and educational staff take part in the Training for the Implementation of Independence of Playing. All development of themes and sub-themes that have been selected must be by the concept of Independence of Playing for children. The assessment is carried out in the form of observation, portfolio.

Keywords:- implementation, Independence of Playing in Curriculum 2013, early childhood education.

I. INTRODUCTION

Early childhood is a child who is at the stage of growth and development. Each child is unique, has advantages in their respective fields, there are those whose language growth is faster than their motor skills and those whose cognitive and social development is very good. At the age of 0-6 years, children will experience rapid growth and development. This is the basis why the 0-6-year period is a golden age or called the golden age. The golden period of brain development in children occurs from the fetus to six years with achievement of about 80%. While 20% occurred in the last 6 years and over.

To support the above, the government makes efforts to develop the golden potential of children with the issuance of Law Number 20 of 2003 Chapter 1, Article 1, point 14 which states that: PAUD is guidance aimed at children from birth to the age of 6 years which is carried out through the provision

of stimulation to help the growth and development of children so that children are ready to enter further education.

The implementation of the educational goals above will be realized if we have an educational design in the form of a curriculum because the curriculum is the overall plan of educational activities. The curriculum contains guidelines and directions about what knowledge, skills, attitudes, or competencies children need to master so that they can become the desired person so that they function well in society. (Zais, 1976:105).

Understanding the curriculum in general from several experts, Schubert (1986). Curriculum Perspective, Paradigm, and Possibility. New York. McMillan Publishing Company provides several definitions, including; "curriculum as content or subject matter, curriculum as a program of planned activities, curriculum as intended learning outcomes, curriculum as cultural reproduction, curriculum as experience, curriculum as discrete tasks and concepts, curriculum as an agenda for social reconstruction". Stratemeyer, Forkner, and McKim (1947) state Curriculum is currently defined in three ways; the courses and class activities in which children and youth engage; the total range of in-class and out class experiences sponsored by the school; and the total life experiences of the learner". It can be concluded that the curriculum is a set of plans and arrangements regarding the objectives, content, learning materials, and methods used as guidelines for implementing learning activities to achieve certain goals. These objectives include national education goals and conformity with the characteristics, conditions, regional potential, educational units, and students.

The curriculum undergoes a process of developing improvements to improve the quality of Indonesian education. The 2013 Curriculum for Early Childhood Education is part of the development of new curriculum improvements. The 2013 curriculum is designed based on independent learning. "In the context of early childhood education, Freedom to Learn is Freedom to Play. Because playing is learning. Now this is an important theme for early childhood that we must continue to strengthen because we want to fight misconceptions for early childhood," said the Director-General of GTK, Ministry of Education and Culture. Starting from the GTK partner activity of the Ministry of Education and Culture of Islamic *PAUD Terpadu Yadiaksa*, implementing the concept of Merdeka Playing Curriculum 2013. The Merdeka Playing activity aims to increase children's imagination, make children think critically, and increase children's creativity.

The application of the second year of independent learning at the *Yadiaksa* Integrated Islamic PAUD The

teacher is an important factor in the implementation of the Independent Learning activities. Observations in the field found that teachers were not from the educational background of teachers in PAUD, in the *Yadiaksa* Islamic Integrated Kindergarten most of them were not from PAUD undergraduate graduates so they did not understand the assessment of the concept of assessment they played.

Based on the Interviewtogether with the teacher, it was revealed that before the implementation of Merdeka Playing the 2013 PAUD curriculum, principals and educators were given online training to prepare the institution for implementing the concept of Merdeka Playing the 2013 curriculum. Departing from the several factors above, the author intends to examine how the implementation of the activities of Merdeka Playing Curriculum 2013 *PAUD Terpadu Yadiaksa*.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study used the descriptive qualitative method. The research location was Integrated Islamic PAUD with three units, namely *Yadiaksa* Integrated Islamic Kindergarten, *Yadiaksa* Integrated Islamic playing-group, and *Yadiaksa* Integrated Islamic daycare.

The technique of data collection is done by interview, observation, and also documentation. Sources of data were obtained from the principal and teachers. Analysis of data in the field Miles and Huberman Model. According to Sugiyono (2012), there were three data analysis activities in the Miles and Huberman model, namely data reduction, data display, and conclusion drawing or verification. Then, the validity of the data was tested through Triangulation, Credibility, Transferability, and Confirmability.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Implementation of the Freedom to Play Curriculum for Early Childhood Education (PAUD) 2013 in Kindergartens, Playgroups, and Child Care Centers. The implementation of each unit is different, and the differences can be seen in the table below:

Unit Name	Implementation of Freedom to Play Curriculum 2013	Constraints Faced in Implementing Free Play Curriculum 2013	Solution for the Implementation of the 2013 Curriculum Free Play	Documentation of Independent Play Activities Curriculum 2013
TK Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa	Headmaster asked all teachers to make RPPM and RPPH 1 week in advance. The children's RPPM and RPPH are used as guidelines for the implementation of Merdeka Play activities. Assessment Techniques Using Direct Performance Appraisal and Portfolio.	The RPPM and RPPH planning formats are difficult for teachers because teachers are not familiar with the concept of independent learning to play the 2013 curriculum.	Before making the RPPM and RPPH tools, the school principal held training beforehand on how to make teachers able to apply to learn freely in the 2013 curriculum.	<p>Figure 1. Freedom to play by making the environment a source of learning (Animal themes, looking for grasshoppers, dragonflies, and animals that live in the leaves)</p>
KB Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa	The manager and the teacher make RPPM, RPPH, and Evaluation. In the implementation of independent play activities, family planning teachers make more use of natural materials and the surrounding environment.	Learning activities use the concept of free play by using tools and materials from the natural surroundings and using the environment around the school as a learning resource.	Freedom to play requires a mature play design so that educators can see the achievement of indicators of each planned, and teachers can observe 6 aspects of development in children	<p>Figure 2. The teacher uses the environment as a place for children to play. On the theme of Healing.</p>
TPA Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa	The application of Freedom to Play for Proper Integrated Islamic Child Care was carried out quite well, because of the guidance from GTK PAUD Dikmas from the Ministry of Education and Culture directly, training on making RPPM, RPPH, and Evaluation tools, in addition, the Integrated Islamic TPA Yadiaksa also received assistance with educational games for children's play.	Learning is more fun for children. However, educators have not been able to thoroughly explore the themed material because the concept of free play has not been used to be included in PBM so far, nutmeg again relates the game to the theme and sub-theme material.	The need for habituation by the teacher so that the theme and sub-theme material delivered is achieved properly. Furthermore, integrated play activities continue to be carried out continuously using material tools, and make the surrounding environment a learning resource.	<p>Figure 3. Educators provide 3 choices for children to play freely to choose the choice of toys they like.</p>

The curriculum functions as a guide in carrying out the learning process. The PAUD curriculum is prepared for

children to provide experiences so that children can develop 6 aspects of their development as their provisions in their

daily lives. As for teachers, the curriculum is used as a working guide in compiling and organizing children's learning experiences. For school principals or managers, the activities of independent play in the 2013 curriculum serve as guidelines in improving the learning situation of Ar-Rahman to be more conducive to providing assistance to children to improve the learning situation, developing the curriculum, and evaluating the progress of learning activities or evaluating standards for the level of achievement of children's development.

Free play activities in the 2013 curriculum have characteristics 1) play activities must arise from within the child himself 2) play activities are free from binding rules even though the teacher plans 3) play activities are comfortable activities that focus on the process 4) Playing activities are dominated by the children themselves and involve the players themselves.

Freedom to play the 2013 curriculum aims to make children have independent personalities. As we know an independent individual is the beginning of an independent and superior nation. Realizing a superior and independent personality must be prepared from an early age through learning that is liberating, independent, intellectual, of course in the form of playing.

Freedom to play can give children the breadth to determine their own goals and play activities in their way. In this case, educators are not the only source of learning. In the independent play activities of the 2013 curriculum, the surrounding environment is a rich tool and game material for children to learn as much as possible. The principle of free play that is meant here is more focused on children understanding the purpose of the activities to be carried out. Children carry out activities independently, children are allowed to reflect on the activities they have done. The role of educators in free play is to involve students in determining the goals of playing activities.

Things that support the implementation of free play are: 1) educators can maximize the use of learning resources, living things, and materials that are around 2) facilitate the choice of play activities related to the environmental context and support three types of play (sensory play, development play), and role-playing). 3) learning with free play can be done with a scientific approach. 4) provide opportunities for children to be more flexible in making works according to the ideas and interests possessed by children, then the teacher can also provide opportunities for children to make works according to the ideas possessed by children and the carrying capacity to convey information on the results works with their materials.

The strength of activity design that we can include in the curriculum is stated by Zais (1976:411-12). First, students have an intrinsic motivation to carry out learning activities because the activities are arranged according to the needs, interests, and desires of students. Students do not need external motivation because the facts, concepts, skills, and processes they learn are useful to them, not because the content is needed for further study or because they will be

tested by the teacher. Second, learning activities are adjusted to the wishes of students. If a group activity is liked by students, he can follow it, but if no activity suits the needs of students, he is allowed to do his project. Third, this design makes students familiar with learning processes that are beneficial for students' lives outside of school.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of the research at TK Islam Terpadu Yadiaksa, Playgroup and Child Care Center obtained a significant conclusion that the implementation of the 2013 curriculum for independent play in the 3 units began with the preparation of the Semester Program learning tools (PROMES), Weekly Learning Implementation Plans (RPPM), Daily Learning Implementation Plans (RPPH), and Assessment Planning. The process of implementing free-to-play learning is carried out at the stage before playing, playing activities, and communicating stages. Principals and teachers work together to design learning tools. Then, communicate the themes, sub-themes, and game ideas that can develop six skills aspect integrated child development. And an assessment will be carried out through observation activities when children are in play activities, portfolio assessments from the results of playing activities, performance, and play assignments.

Constraints or difficulties faced by teachers in compiling learning tools are due to teachers with backgrounds that are not early childhood education, lack of competence of teachers, teachers have not mastered technology well and information regarding the implementation of independent activities to play PAUD 2013 curriculum. holding training workshops with the Ministry of Education and Culture. If the principal does not find significant obstacles in the implementation of free play activities, then the principal will contact the school supervisor besides that the teacher can also share with fellow teachers implementing the 2013 curriculum.

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